

Identification of Factors Influencing Teachers' Perceived Self-Efficacy in Inclusive Education

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Abstract

Teacher effectiveness in inclusive education is a crucial factor influencing teachers' beliefs that they can adapt teaching approaches and methods to meet the needs of every student. The aim of this research is to identify the factors that influence teachers' perceived self-efficacy in inclusive education. The sample consists of subject teachers (N=85) and classroom teachers (N=154) from primary schools in the Sarajevo Canton. To assess teachers' perceived self-efficacy in inclusive education, the Teacher Efficacy for Inclusive Practices (TEIP) questionnaire was used. The results indicate that there are certain differences in perceived self-efficacy based on gender ($p < 0.05$). Female participants rated their self-efficacy higher compared to male participants. Teachers tend to perceive their self-efficacy less positively as their age increases. It was observed that there is no difference in perceived self-efficacy between teachers who attended professional development programs and those who did not.

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Introduction

Teachers' perceptions of their own work, competencies, and outcomes are defined as teacher efficacy (Barni et al., 2019). Teachers primarily evaluate their work through student success. However, many other factors influence teachers' perceptions of their own efficacy, such as school climate, professional development, and the willingness and effort of teachers to conduct lessons in a way that allows every student to succeed. Teachers who invest more time and effort in lesson planning, use various teaching methods, and evaluate their own work based on student feedback tend to perceive themselves as more effective (Woodcock, Sharma, Subban & Hitches, 2022). Efficacy can be observed as general and personal efficacy (Tschannen-Moran & Hoy, 2001). General efficacy refers to a teacher's belief that, by using available resources and collaborating with colleagues and support staff within the school, they can provide each student with an approach that leads to good academic achievement. On the other hand, personal efficacy refers to teachers' beliefs in their ability to respond to various challenges and their capability to teach students with social and emotional difficulties, including students with developmental disabilities (Bandura, 1997). These beliefs are shaped by various factors and influence how teachers approach their work and their level of commitment (Bandura, 1981). Unlike self-efficacy, which is a subjective perception of an individual who believes they are ready and able to achieve set goals, efficacy implies that the individual possesses the necessary skills and abilities to achieve those goals.

Teacher efficacy shapes their behavior, influences classroom climate, and affects teachers' beliefs about students' abilities and potential (Malinen & Savoalinen, 2024). In the context of inclusive education, this definition implies that teachers with a positive perception of their efficacy can provide students with developmental disabilities appropriate teaching methods and necessary accommodations. In contrast, teachers who perceive themselves as less effective in inclusive education tend not to attempt applying different principles and methods in teaching, driven by the belief that they lack the skills and abilities to teach students with disabilities (Sharma et al., 2012).

Inclusive education is defined as education for all, which implies the inclusion of all children at all levels of upbringing and education (Guidelines for Inclusion, 2006). At the same time, it involves a change in teaching approach and methodology, which is a fundamental requirement of the "education for all" concept. Booth and Ainscow (2002) emphasize that inclusion is an ongoing process that provides every student with the opportunity to be educated under equal conditions.

Teachers often highlight the lack of competencies for teaching students with various developmental disabilities as the biggest challenge in inclusive education. On the other hand, the most important role of teachers in inclusive education is their willingness to accept students with developmental disabilities and to apply diverse teaching methods (Ivančić, 2012). Teaching students with developmental disabilities does not require special or extraordinary activities, but rather tasks and activities that are aligned with the classroom curriculum. This means that the teacher should integrate the educational goals for students with disabilities into regular classroom activities in a way that enables the student to make progress in acquiring knowledge, skills, and abilities.

By using various adaptations, the teacher does not change the nature of the task but facilitates learning for the student with disabilities and removes the barriers that hinder or prevent learning

due to the student's developmental challenges. The teacher in an inclusive classroom assumes multiple roles. In addition to planning the teaching process, the teacher acts as a mentor in the classroom, collaborates with other teachers, support staff, and parents, and plays a significant role in fostering positive attitudes and promoting acceptance of diversity.

From the very first day, the teacher observes student development, records how the student functions, and identifies obstacles that hinder learning. To be successful in fulfilling all tasks in inclusive education, the teacher must be capable of adapting instructional approaches, applying various support strategies tailored to each student, and using available resources effectively.

The changes required by the concept of inclusive education primarily relate to strengthening teachers' competencies, which go beyond traditional teaching methods. In order to effectively meet the demands of inclusive education, teachers must possess a variety of teaching skills and abilities, but also believe that they are capable of successfully performing tasks and activities in inclusive classrooms. In other words, teachers' behavior in inclusive settings depends largely on their perception of their own efficacy. A teacher may respond to the demands of inclusive education with more or less ease, and that experience directly influences their behavior. Teachers with a high sense of efficacy tend to experience greater job satisfaction, lower levels of stress, and are better equipped to manage challenging student behaviors (Zee & Koomen, 2016).

Studies have shown that there are numerous factors influencing teachers' perceived self-efficacy in inclusion (Tschannen & Hoy, 2001; Wray, Sharma & Subban, 2022). Tschannen and Hoy (2001) highlight three specific factors: efficacy in instruction, efficacy in predicting and managing undesirable behaviors, and efficacy in using diverse strategies to achieve educational goals. Teacher efficacy for inclusive education is influenced by various demographic factors, teachers' attitudes and beliefs, teacher competencies, school climate, and experience interacting with persons with disabilities (Wray et al., 2022).

The scale for assessing teachers' perceived self-efficacy in inclusive education (Sharma et al., 2012) consists of three subscales: Efficacy in implementing inclusive instruction, Efficacy in managing undesirable behaviors, and Efficacy in collaboration with others.

Studies have shown that a high perception of self-efficacy in inclusive education does not necessarily mean that a teacher will fully utilize their skills and abilities when teaching students with developmental disabilities. It appears that teacher efficacy in inclusive education, despite being a highly important construct, is often overlooked, and little is being done to enhance teacher effectiveness in inclusive classrooms — and thereby improve inclusive education as a whole (Sharma & George, 2016).

The aim of this study is to identify the factors that influence teachers' perceptions of their own efficacy in inclusive education.

Methods

Participants

The study involved a total of 239 teachers, including 154 primary (classroom) teachers and 85 subject teachers. The research was conducted in 2023 in elementary schools across the Sarajevo Canton. Out of the total number of participants (N=239), 35 were male (14.64%) and 204 were female (85.35%). Regarding work experience, 96 participants (40.17%) had between 21 and 30

years of teaching experience, while the smallest group consisted of 16 teachers (6.69%) with over 30 years of experience.

A large number of respondents, 212 (88.7%), had attended professional development programs for teachers, while 27 (11.2%) had not.

Instruments

The study used the Teacher Efficacy for Inclusive Practices (TEIP) questionnaire developed by Sharma et al. (2012) to assess teachers' perceptions of their own efficacy in inclusive education. The questionnaire contains 18 items grouped into three subscales: Efficacy in implementing inclusive instruction, Efficacy in managing undesirable behaviors, Efficacy in collaboration with others. Responses were measured using a 6-point Likert scale: 1 – Strongly disagree, 2 – Disagree, 3 – Somewhat disagree, 4 – Somewhat agree, 5 – Agree, 6 – Strongly agree.

Factor analysis identified three distinct factors, with Cronbach's alpha coefficients ranging from 0.85 to 0.93, while the overall reliability coefficient of the instrument was 0.89 (Sharma et al., 2014). The questionnaire was administered online using Google Forms, and participation was completely anonymous.

Results

Teacher Efficacy in Inclusive Education

The results presented in Table 1 refer to the scale values for assessing teachers' efficacy across all three dimensions of efficacy. Teachers are the cornerstone of inclusive education, as their role requires skills and abilities that, when utilized, foster their professional growth and development, while also influencing the achievement of inclusive education goals.

Table 1. *Mean Values of Teachers' Perceived Efficacy*

ON	Factor	M	SD	Med	V
1	Efficacy in implementing inclusive instruction	4,46	1,41	5	1,99
2	Efficacy in managing undesirable behaviors	4,58	1,33	5	1,78
3	Efficacy in collaboration with others	4,69	1,25	5	1,58

When observing the table, it is evident that the highest efficacy is found in collaboration with others, where we also observe the lowest variability in responses ($V = 1.5$). The dimension in which teachers demonstrate the lowest efficacy is the implementation of inclusive instruction, with very diverse responses from the participants ($SD = 1.4$).

Teachers acquire competencies for inclusive education not only through theoretical frameworks but also through professional development, where they gain practical skills for applying various strategies in the classroom.

Teacher Professional Development

Table 2. T-test and Arithmetic Mean of Teachers' Perceived Efficacy in Classroom and Subject Teachers in Relation to Professional Development

Professional Development	Number	M	SE	Lower 95% Interval	Upper 95% Interval	t-test
Yes	212	82,87	1,08	80,7	85,0	1.3*
No	27	78,70	3,01	72,7	84,7	

Note * p = 0,20.

Table 2 presents the results of the t-test and the mean values of perceived efficacy in relation to professional development. Respondents who participated in professional development programs scored slightly higher. The difference in the t-test results (1.3) and p=0.20 is not statistically significant. Although the sample is not uniform, we observe that there is no difference in the perception of own efficacy between teachers who have attended and those who have not attended professional development programs.

Teacher Age

In our education system, teacher age is a variable that can influence teacher efficacy. There are several reasons supporting this statement. The positive influence of teacher age relates to the positive experiences in inclusive practice and the self-confidence they have developed in facing various challenges. On the other hand, the negative influence of age relates to the lack of formal education on inclusion and resistance to change. The total correlation between teachers' age and self-efficacy is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Correlation Between Respondent Age and Perceived Efficacy in All Teachers

The results of the correlation analysis of the impact of respondents' age on their perceived efficacy show that the correlation is $r=0.15$, which is very low but statistically significant with $p=0.02$.

Figure 2. *Correlation Between Age and Perceived Efficacy Among Classroom Teachers*

In Figure 2, the results of the correlation between the age of classroom teachers and their perceived efficacy are shown. In this case, no significant statistical correlation was observed, as $r=-0.14$ and $p=0.09$.

Figure 3. *Correlation Between Age and Perceived Efficacy Among Subject Teachers*

We obtained somewhat different results when analyzing the correlation between the age of the respondents and their perceived efficacy among subject teachers (Figure 3). A decline in perceived efficacy was observed with age among subject teachers. The correlation value is $r=-0.22$, and although it is low, it is statistically significant with $p=0.04$. Among classroom teachers, no correlation was found between these two variables, whereas with subject teachers, a decline in efficacy was noted with increasing age.

Gender of Teachers

We also analyzed the impact of gender on the efficacy of classroom and subject teachers. Among both classroom and subject teachers, female respondents achieved higher results in their perception of their own efficacy.

Table 3. *T-test and Mean Perceived Efficacy by Teachers' Gender*

Gender	Number	M	SE	Lower 95% Interval	Upper 95% Interval	t-test
Male	35	78.0	2,7	72,7	83,2	1.8*
Female	204	83.2	1,1	81.0	85,3	

Note * $p = 0,03$.

It was observed that female participants feel more effective than male participants, with t-test values of 1.8 and $p=0.03$. We specifically analyzed the impact of gender on teacher effectiveness for both groups of participants. In both groups of participants, although small, a statistically significant difference in the perception of effectiveness based on gender was observed. Female participants feel more effective in both groups of teachers, with values for classroom teachers (t-test=1.7, $p=0.04$) and subject teachers (t-test=0.24, $p=0.04$).

Table 4. *T-test and Mean Score of Self-Efficacy Perception by Gender for Classroom Teachers*

Gender	Number	M	SE	Lower 95% interval	Upper 95% Interval	t-test
Male	10	75,7	5,1	65,7	85,8	1.7*
Female	143	84,6	1,3	82,0	87,3	

Note * $p = 0,04$.

Table 5. *T-test and Mean Score of Self-Efficacy Perception by Gender for Subject Teachers*

Gender	Number	M	SE	Lower 95% interval	Upper 95% Interval	t-test
Male	25	78,9	3,0	72,9	84,9	0,24*
Female	61	79,7	1,9	75,9	83,6	

Note * $p = 0,04$.

Discussion

This research was conducted to identify the factors influencing teachers' self-efficacy perception in inclusive education. The results show that there are differences in teachers' perceptions regarding the dimensions of teacher efficacy in inclusive education. Teachers perceive themselves as least effective in the dimension of applying inclusive instructions. Teachers acquire competencies and knowledge about the principles of inclusive education during their university education, through experience working with students with developmental disabilities, and through professional development. It is assumed that the causes of the low perception of this type of efficacy are rooted in teacher education. In a study conducted by Loreman et al. (2013), the results showed differences in teachers' self-efficacy perception based on teacher education ($p < 0.01$). They observed that teachers with strong theoretical knowledge and more practical experience had higher levels of efficacy.

There are no statistically significant differences in the perception of efficacy between teachers who have attended professional development programs and those who have not. However, the question remains as to why there is no difference in efficacy perception. Scanlon and Barnes-Holmes (2013) report on the impact of teacher professional development on competencies in working with students with emotional development difficulties and behavioral issues ($p < 0.01$). Professional development had a significant impact on the perception of efficacy in applying strategies to include students with developmental difficulties in educational activities ($p = 0.01$) (Reyes et al., 2017). No differences were observed in the perception of efficacy based on the age of the participants, but a decline in efficacy was noted among subject teachers with increasing age. The positive impact of age on teacher efficacy is found in the research by Ekins et al. (2016) and Subban et al. (2021). The results of these studies show that older teachers have a higher level of efficacy for inclusive education. However, the results of other studies indicate that age is not correlated with self-efficacy perception (Schwab et al., 2017).

In the study of the impact of gender on teacher efficacy, the results are somewhat inconsistent, as some studies confirm differences in the perception of efficacy based on gender, while others report that gender has no significant impact on teachers' perceptions of efficacy in inclusive education. The results of our study show that female participants rated their own efficacy higher than male participants. A review of the literature reveals that the findings of our study are similar to those reported by San et al. (2021) and Specht et al. (2016), with values of $p < 0.05$.

Study Limitations

There are several limitations in this study. The first limitation concerns the sample size. In our study, 7.59% of the total population of teachers in primary schools in the Sarajevo Canton participated. The sample consisted of a larger number of primary school teachers, as well as a larger number of female participants. A significantly higher number of teachers had attended professional development programs compared to those who had not. The limitations of this study should certainly be taken into account in future research, where it would be desirable to have a more balanced sample of both primary and subject teachers, as well as a more equal distribution of gender. An especially interesting finding is that there is no difference in the perception of teacher efficacy based on professional development, so future studies would benefit from investigating the reasons behind the uniform perceptions of efficacy among teachers who participated in professional development programs and those who did not.

Recommendations for future research also include a detailed investigation into why the perception of teachers' efficacy decreases with increasing age.

Conclusion

The results show that there are differences in teachers' perceptions of their own efficacy in inclusive education. Respondents perceive the lowest efficacy within the dimension related to the application of inclusive instructions. There is no difference in the perception of efficacy in relation to teachers' professional development. Female respondents perceive themselves as more efficient. A decrease in efficacy was observed among subject teachers with increasing age, while for primary school teachers, age has no impact on the perception of efficacy.

Conflict of interest.

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this manuscript.

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